

Adsorption of Acids by Animal Charcoal.

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Adsorption of acids by animal charcoal has long been accepted by chemists, and recently several mechanisms have been suggested as explanations of this phenomenon. The following experiment helps to demonstrate the mechanism of the so-called acid adsorption by animal charcoal.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2 G. of animal charcoal (65% ash) were shaken with 100 c.c. of approximately $N/20$ -acetic acid for 20 minutes. Another 2 g. of the same charcoal were shaken with 100 c.c. of approximately $N/20$ -HCl for 20 minutes. The solutions were then centrifuged from the charcoal which settled out. The supernatant liquid and the stock solution of $N/20$ -acetic acid were titrated for acidity; the supernatant liquid and the stock solution of $N/20$ -HCl were titrated for acidity and chlorine content. All quantities of the acid solutions were pipetted out. The chlorine was determined by the Whitehorn modification of the Volhard method (Whitehorn, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1921, **45**, 449).

Reduction in acidity.

Solutions.	Quantity of soln.	Titre (average).
Stock soln.	20 c.c. $N/20$ (approx.) acetic acid	10.60 c.c. $N/10$ -NaOH
„ „	„ $N/20$ -HCl	11.36 „ $N/10$ -NaOH
Centrifuged soln.	„ „ -acetic acid	6.09 „ „ „
„ „	„ „ -HCl	6.44 „ „ „

The centrifuged solutions gave a strong qualitative test for phosphates.

Non-reduction in chlorine concentration.

Solution.	Quantity of soln.	Titre (average).
Stock soln.	2 c.c. ($N/20$) (approx.) HCl	6.60 c.c. $AgNO_3$
Centrifuged soln.	„ „ „ „	6.65 c.c. „

HCl factor $\equiv 1.136 N/20$; $AgNO_3$ solution contains 0.002905 g./c.c. $AgNO_3$

Animal charcoal acts similarly upon $N/20\text{-HCl}$ and acetic acids: the reduction of hydrogen concentrations is approximately the same for both acids. Animal charcoal does *not* reduce the chlorine content of HCl . It, therefore, does not adsorb HCl but reacts with it in a manner described previously (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1932, 9, 907); the phosphate impurities of this charcoal are converted to phosphoric acid by the action with HCl , and thus, a partially untitratable hydrogen results. The chlorine anion remains quantitatively unaffected by this reaction.

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